

The mobility of protons in urea nitrate crystals changes the electroneutrality of cadmium oxide and causes the displacement of Cd^{2+} ions which in turn combine with the nitrate present at the interphase resulting in the formation of cadmium nitrate. These steps occurring at the points of contact of the two solids are soon followed by the bulk reaction because of the movement of nitrate ions from the bulk which in turn takes place due to the concentration gradient set up by the removal of nitrate ions at the surface. Thus protonation of cadmium oxide as a result of the mobility of hydrogen ions from urea nitrate leaves behind urea at the end of the reaction. In the beginning due to nucleation process cadmium nitrate is formed in the vicinity of the original interface which soon spreads to the entire bulk on account of small particle size of the reactants. Since the volume of the particle is very small compared to its surface area, the nucleation process would completely consume the total volume of the reactants.

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Stepwise Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Function of Zn(II) and Cd(II) Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenoneanil

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Manuscript received 19 July 1977, revised 4 September 1978
accepted 8 September 1978

IN continuation of our previous communications^{2,3} herein, we describe potentiometric studies on chelates of 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenoneanil (HCBA) with Zn(II) and Cd(II) in 60% v/v dioxan water media at $\mu=0.1M$ at 25°, 30° and 35°.

Experimental

The expanded scale pH meter of Systronic with a wide range (0.01 pH) glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements.

The ligand 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenoneanil was synthesised by condensing 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzophenone with aniline. It was crystallised from alcohol ; m. p. 148°.

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. AnalaR grade. The potentiometric titration was carried out in an inert atmosphere using carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution and the constant ionic strength was maintained by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate solution. The Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique^{4,5} as used by Irving and Rossotti¹ has been applied to determine the protonation constants of the ligand and the formation constants of complexes. The log K values were computed by various computational methods as summarised in Table-1. The linear plots of $\log \frac{\bar{n}A}{1-\bar{n}A}$ vs B for ligand and formation curves of Zn(II) and Cd(II) chelates are shown in figures 1, 2, and 3 respectively.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\frac{\bar{n}A}{1-\bar{n}A}$ vs B of 2-Hydroxy-5-Chlorobenzophenoneanil at 25°, 30° and 35°.

Fig. 2. Formation curves of Zn(HCBA)₂ at 25°, 30° and 35°.

Fig. 3 Formation curves of Cd(HCBH)₂ at 25°, 30° and 35°.

The values of the changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying the

metal ligand complex forming reactions have been calculated at 25°, 30°, and 35° using the relations

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K$$

$$\frac{d \log K}{d(1/T)} = \frac{\Delta H}{4.57}$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

These are summarised in Table-2.

It is concluded that with the change in temperature there was no appreciable change in the value of stability constants.

The stability constant of Zn(II) complex is higher than that of Cd(II) complex which is in agreement with Irving-Williams order⁶.

TABLE-1 STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ZN(II) AND CD(II) CHELATES OF 2-HYDROXY-BENZOPHENONE ANIL AT $\mu=0.1M$ IN 60% V/V DIOXANE-WATER MEDIA.

Chelates	Temp. °C.		Methods			
			least square	linearplot	pointwise	half integral
Zn(HCBA) ₂	25	logK ₁	7.92	7.92	7.93	7.92
		logK	5.43	5.44	5.49	5.40
		log/β	13.35	13.36	13.42	13.32
Zn(HCBA) ₂	30	logK ₁	7.84	7.88	7.87	7.84
		logK ₂	5.28	5.30	5.10	5.32
		log/β	13.12	13.18	12.97	13.16
Zn(HCBA) ₂	35	logK ₁	7.72	7.72	7.75	7.73
		logK ₂	5.22	5.30	5.14	5.13
		log/β	12.94	13.02	12.89	12.86
Cd(HCBA) ₂	25	logK ₁	7.78	7.80	7.82	7.80
		logK ₂	5.33	5.32	5.31	5.32
		log/β	13.11	13.12	13.13	13.12
Cd(HCBA) ₂	30	logK ₁	7.72	7.74	7.75	7.70
		logK ₂	5.19	5.18	5.14	5.18
		log/β	12.91	12.92	12.89	12.88
Cd(HCBA) ₂	35	logK ₁	7.55	7.55	7.58	7.57
		logK ₂	5.14	5.05	5.07	5.07
		log/β	12.69	12.66	12.65	12.64
HCBA	25	-	10.90	10.90	10.90	
HCBA	30	-	10.84	10.85	10.86	
HCBA	35	-	10.79	10.80	10.81	

TABLE-2 THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF ZN(II) AND CD(II) CHELATES OF 2-HYDROXY-5-CHLOROBENZOPHENONE ANIL AT $\mu=0.1M$ IN 60% V/V DIOXANE-WATER MEDIA.

Chelate	Temp. °C	log β average	G K cal./mole	H K cal./mole	S (e. u.)
Zn(HCBA) ₂	25	13.36	-18.22	-20.11	-6.34
Zn(HCBA) ₂	30	13.12	-18.19	-20.11	-6.34
Zn(HCBA) ₂	35	12.88	-18.16	-20.11	-6.33
Cd(HCBA) ₂	25	13.12	-17.90	-21.34	-11.54
Cd(HCBA) ₂	30	12.89	-17.88	-21.34	-11.42
Cd(HCBA) ₂	35	12.65	-17.83	-21.34	-11.40

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. K. A. Thaker, Head of the Chemistry Department for providing necessary research facilities. We are also thankful to Saurashtra University for the Scholarship to Y.Z.P.

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Solubility Measurements with Zinc Phosphates

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Manuscript received 1 July 1978, accepted 14 September 1978

THE role of zinc in plant nutrition has been well established by several workers¹. The availability of zinc to the plants depends on various factors. Since zinc is absorbed in the ionic form its ionic concentration is the most important factor. Water soluble zinc salts are, therefore, preferred for zinc fertilisation. But the soil conditions must be favourable for high ionic concentration of zinc. This condition is not generally fulfilled especially in soils heavily fertilised with phosphates. It has been suggested that zinc may be rendered unavailable by being precipitated as sparingly soluble zinc phosphate². In order to understand the implications of this hypothesis, it is necessary to determine the solubility of zinc phosphate under conditions which usually obtain in the soil, namely, the pH which may range from alkaline to acid, and the composition of zinc phosphate which may also vary. Moreover, the physical forms of the zinc phosphate may vary depending on the age of the precipitate moistness of the soil and concentration of zinc and phosphate ions, etc.

The different possible forms may be several but those which have been used here are :

i) zinc phosphate in finely divided condition to simulate a fresh precipitate in the moist state of the soil ;

ii) a freshly formed crystalline zinc phosphate ;

iii) a laboratory sample which represents an aged sample in crystalline form and simulates the form likely to be present in soils under long-term fertilization with zinc and phosphate.

The different forms of zinc phosphate have been prepared³ in the following manner :

1) The finely divided form is prepared by mixing a somewhat concentrated solution of zinc sulphate (66 g in 150 ml water) with disodium hydrogen phosphate (57 g in 150 ml water) keeping the phosphate in slight excess. The suspension so formed is dialysed against double-distilled water in a cellophane bag to make it free from soluble salts.

2) About 66 g of recrystallised zinc sulphate in 250 ml water is mixed slowly with constant stirring with 57 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate in 250 ml water. The whole thing is allowed to be heated over slow flame for about fifteen days during which the precipitate becomes coarse-grained. The precipitate is washed several times with water by decantation to make it free from soluble salts. The precipitated zinc phosphate is pressed between filter papers and dried in oven at 105-110°.

3) A laboratory sample of zinc phosphate is thoroughly desiccated and stored in a bottle.

The samples were analysed for zinc and phosphate. The composition of all the three samples corresponds to $Zn_3(PO_4)_2$.

The solubility measurements are carried out at 3 pH's.

About 0.05 g each form of zinc phosphate is taken in well-stoppered conical flasks (treated scrupulously with caustic soda solution and then nitric acid to make it free from zinc ions) containing : (a) 100 ml double-distilled water ; (b) 100 ml double-distilled water plus 2 drops of 0.1N sulphuric acid ; and (c) 100 ml double-distilled water plus 2 drops of 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

Each experiment is run in duplicate along with a blank in which only water with acid/alkali was taken. The bottles are shaken thoroughly in a mechanical shaker for 12-15 hr to allow equilibrium to be attained. The temperatures of the solutions are noted and pH's measured. The pH of (a) i.e. water medium is about 6.65, while those of (b) and (c), i.e. acidified and alkaline media range from 4.95-5.00 & 8.4-8.5 respectively. The solutions are filtered through G4 sintered filter tip under mild suction. The acidified solutions are diluted ten times but the neutral and alkaline solutions are taken as such for measurements. For zinc determination the standard zinc dithizonate complex⁴ method has been used by referring to standard calibration curve obtained by using zinc sulphate solution containing 2.3 μ g of zinc.

For phosphate determination⁵ the method of stannous chloride reduction of phosphomolybdic acid has been used. The calibration curve has been obtained with solutions containing 0.05-0.6 ppm of P.